

Theme: The role and essence of banking services in Islamic financing

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Abstract. This article explores the essential role and significance of Islamic banks in fostering economic growth and financial inclusion. By adhering to principles that prohibit interest and promote risk-sharing, Islamic finance offers innovative solutions for both individuals and businesses. Additionally, we will delve into the key concepts that underpin this system, such as profit-sharing, ethical investments, and asset-backed financing. Understanding these principles is crucial for grasping how Islamic finance not only meets the financial needs of its users but also contributes to a more just and sustainable economic environment.

Keywords: Islamic banking, riba, Gharar, maisir, haram, istihalah, ethical investment, Islamic principles.

Introduction. The practices of Islamic banking are usually traced back to businesspeople in the Middle East who started engaging in financial transactions with their European counterparts during the Medieval era.

At first, they used the same financial principles as the Europeans. However, over time, as trading systems developed and European countries started establishing local branches of their banks in the Middle East, some of these banks adopted the local customs of the region where they were newly established, primarily no-interest financial systems that worked on a profit-and-loss sharing method.

By adopting these practices, these European banks could also serve the needs of local businesspeople who were Muslim. Beginning in the 1960s, Islamic banking resurfaced in

the modern world, and since 1975, many new interest-free banks have opened. Though the majority of these Islamic banking institutions were founded in Muslim countries, Islamic banks also opened in Western Europe during the early 1980s. In addition, national interest-free banking systems have been developed by the governments of Iran, Sudan, and (to a lesser extent) Pakistan.

The Mit-Ghamr Savings Bank, established in 1963 in Egypt, is commonly referred to as the first example of Islamic banking in the modern world. When Mit-Ghamr lent money to businesses, it did so based on a profit-sharing model. The Mit-Ghamr project was closed in 1967 due to political factors, but during its year of operations, the bank exercised a great deal of caution, only approving about 40% of its business loan applications. However, in economically good times, the bank's default ratio was said to be zero.

Islamic banking, also referred to as Islamic finance or Shariah-compliant finance, refers to financial activities that adhere to Shariah (Islamic law). Two fundamental principles of Islamic banking are the sharing of profit and loss and the prohibition of the collection and payment of interest by lenders and investors.

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Some conventional banks have windows or sections that provide designated Islamic banking services to their customers.

There are more than 560 banks and over 1,900 mutual funds around the world that comply with Islamic principles. Between 2015 and 2021, Islamic financial assets grew to about \$4 trillion from \$2.17 trillion and are projected to rise to roughly \$5.9 trillion by 2026,

according to a 2022 report by the Islamic Corporation for the Development of Private Sector (ICD) and Refinitiv.

This growth is largely due to the rising economies of Muslim countries (especially those that have benefited from oil price increases). The global Islamic finance industry grew in 2021 and 2022 due to increased bond issuance and a continuing economic recovery in the financial markets, according to S&P Global Ratings. Islamic assets also managed to expand over 10% in 2020, despite the pandemic.

Islamic banking is grounded in the tenets of the Islamic faith as they relate to commercial transactions. The principles of Islamic banking are derived from the Quran, which is the central religious text of Islam. In Islamic banking, all transactions must comply with Shariah, the legal code of Islam (based on the teachings of the Quran). The rules that govern commercial transactions in Islamic banking are referred to as *fiqh al-muamalat*.

Employees of institutions that abide by Islamic banking are trusted to not deviate from the fundamental principles of the Quran while they are conducting business. When more information or guidance is necessary, Islamic bankers turn to learned scholars or use independent reasoning based on scholarship and customary practices.

To earn money without the typical practice of charging interest, Islamic banks use equity participation systems, which are similar to profit sharing. Equity participation means if a bank lends money to a business, the business will pay back the loan without interest and instead give the bank a share in its profits. If the business defaults or doesn't earn a profit, then the bank also doesn't get paid.

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There are many differences between Islamic and mainstream finance, but two of the most important are the methods of sharing profit and loss, and the prohibition of the collection and payment of interest by lenders and investors. Shariah also prohibits taking interest on

loans. Islamic banks make a profit through equity participation, which requires a borrower to give the bank a share in their profits, rather than paying interest.

Prohibition of Interest (Riba): Islamic finance prohibits the payment and receipt of interest. Instead, financial transactions should be based on profit-sharing, risk-sharing, or fee-based arrangements.

Riba is prohibited in Islam in all its forms whatever its rate may be. It should be remembered that the word *riba*, which means an excess or addition over and above the principal, covers both usury and interest, whether the dealing is with an individual, or with a bank, or with any other organization.

The Arabic word ***Gharar*** is a fairly broad concept that literally means deceit, risk, fraud, uncertainty or hazard that might lead to destruction or loss.

Asset-Backed Financing: Islamic finance emphasizes the use of tangible assets as collateral or underlying assets in financial transactions. This principle ensures that transactions are linked to real economic activities and assets.

Prohibition of Speculation (Maisir): Islamic finance discourages speculative practices that involve excessive uncertainty or gambling-like elements. Transactions should be based on genuine trade and investment activities.

Prohibition of Prohibited Activities (Haram): Islamic finance avoids investments in activities that are considered harmful or prohibited under Shariah, such as alcohol, gambling, tobacco, and other unethical industries.

Sharing of Profit and Loss: Islamic finance promotes the sharing of both profits and losses between the parties involved in a financial transaction. This principle encourages a fair distribution of risk and reward.

Ethical Investment: Islamic finance encourages investments in socially responsible and ethical sectors that align with Islamic values, such as renewable energy, healthcare, education, and community development.

Avoidance of Excessive Debt: Islamic finance promotes responsible borrowing and discourages excessive debt. It encourages individuals and businesses to avoid overleveraging and to engage in sustainable financial practices.

These principles guide the development of various Islamic financial instruments and services, such as profit-sharing contracts (*Mudarabah*), partnership contracts (*Musharakah*), cost-plus financing (*Murabaha*), leasing (*Ijara*), and equity-based investments (*Sukuk*).

Here, it should be mentioned that we carried out a brief poll to learn what our institute's students thought about Islamic banking, Islamic finance, and their operations in our nation. The following are the study's findings:

Graph 1 shows that 71.6 percent of the total respondents have knowledge about Islamic banks, while 17.9 percent have no knowledge about Islamic financial institutions. The rest said that they are interested in Islamic banks and want to get information about it.

Graph 1

In the second pie chart, "Have you heard about any Islamic financial organization operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan?" - the answers to the question are reflected. According to him, 46.5% of people know about Islamic organizations operating in our country, and almost as many people do not have information about it (41.1%). It seems that the rest simply do not have an understanding of Islamic financial institutions.

Graph 2

When asked the next question about the difference between Islamic banks and conventional banks, only 1 percent of respondents said that there is no difference, while all the rest were aware of the differences between conventional and Islamic banks.

The next graph shows that 67.7 percent (almost 65 people) out of 100 of the population of our country said that if Islamic banks start operating in our country, they would prefer to use these banking services, while 11.5 percent chose the services of traditional banks.

At the last stage, opinions were asked about the future of Islamic banks in our country and in the world as a whole. Almost all participants expressed the opinion that the future of Islamic banks is bright, they will develop rapidly, especially in the future, the demand for Islamic banks will increase in Muslim countries, and in the next 20 years, these banks will open a new era of development. Some of them said that because they have not yet used the services of Islamic banks, they still prefer traditional banks, and if they try using the services of Islamic banks, they may change their minds.

In conclusion, Islamic banking services play a vital role in Islamic financing by providing ethical and Shariah-compliant financial solutions. These services cater to the unique needs of individuals and businesses who value adherence to Islamic principles in their financial transactions. With their impact on the economy and promising future prospects, Islamic banking services will continue to shape the financial landscape and contribute to the sustainable development of our country and the world.

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